

METHODS FOR CONTROLLING THE EXCITATION OF SYNCHRONOUS MOTORS OF PUMPING STATIONS USING AUTOMATIC REGULATORS BASED ON NEURAL NETWORKS

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The expression for the transfer function of proportional control is

$$\frac{U}{\Delta U_1} = K_p, \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta U_1 = U_{ref} - U_t(t),$$

where

U – exit; ΔU_1 – entrance; K_p - proportional control coefficient; U_{ref} - proportional control coefficient; $U_t(t)$ - averaging of effective values of voltage at the generator terminals in real time [3,4].

Expression for the transfer function of PID control based on the generator voltage deviation:

$$\frac{U}{\Delta U_1} = (K_p + K_{Ds}) \frac{1}{1 + K_{Is}}, \quad (2)$$

where K_p , K_I , K_D - proportional, integral and differential control coefficients, respectively [5].

The block diagrams of the transfer functions of the closed system corresponding to equations (1) and (2) are shown in figures 1 and 2, respectively.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proportional control function.

Fig.2. Block diagram of the PID control transfer function.

The PID control shown in figure 2 has been further refined. As can be seen from equation (2), the transfer function of PID control consists of the sum of the proportional element K_p and the differential element K_{Ds} , connected in series with the inertial element $\frac{1}{1 + K_{Is}}$. If the time constant

of the inertial element is large enough or $K_{Is} \ll 1$, the value 1 can be ignored. Here, the inertial

element is similar to the integral element $\frac{1}{K_{Is}}$. Thus, the control mode can be called a PID control system based on the generator voltage deviation [6].

The essence of the proposed control approach is shown in Figure 1, which depicts a functional diagram of a synchronous motor powered from the grid, in which the proposed excitation control approach is implemented based on fuzzy logic in neural networks. The idea of membership in a set is used in decision making under uncertainty. Membership can take a value from 0 to 1. Different types of membership functions can be used for analysis, such as trapezoidal, triangular, sigmoidal, Gaussian, etc. The structure of the Fuzzy logic controller formation is shown in Fig. 1 [6,7]

Thus, a synchronous motor equipped with a fuzzy controller, PID regulators as an AEC system, is able to dampen fluctuations in transient processes and maintain operating parameters at nominal levels.

The use of the compensation capabilities of a synchronous motor is relevant both from the point of view of minimizing energy losses and from the point of view of meeting the requirements of power systems for an acceptable level of reactive load of consumers during hours of maximum active load, thereby ensuring the stability of power systems.